

PROCESSING OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Two models for the deposition of ceramic matrix within a ceramic fibrous preform from the chemical reactions have been examined in this paper. The first model considers the ceramic matrix deposition within a ceramic fiber bundle; in this case, vapor diffusion, chemical reaction on the inner surface of the capillary, deposition film growth, porosity, and effects of reactant compositions at various reactor temperature and pressure have been taken into account. The second model considers the ceramic matrix deposition within a 3-dimensional woven preform under both temperature and pressure gradients. The velocity and temperature profiles of the preform have been determined.

INTRODUCTION

During the past decade, many fabrication methods for ceramic/ceramic composites have been proposed. Among these processing routes, a relatively low-stress and low-temperature chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) technique has been reported. The CVI process involves the infiltration of vapors into a fibrous preform and the deposition of a solid product from the chemical reaction of the vapor species to form the matrix of the composite. The matrix growth rate is affected by the conditions of the reactor, the nature of the reactant composition, the microstructure of the fibrous preform, and the type of the vapor infiltration.

Two types of fabrication route by CVI have been proposed in ceramic/ceramic composites manufacturing. The first is an isothermal process. In this route, vapor species infiltrate into the fibrous preform by diffusion; the concentration gradient of reactants results in a deposition gradient which causes the premature closure of the diffusion path near the preform surface. The second process applies a pressure and temperature gradient within the fibrous preform¹⁻³. The density gradient within the preform thus can be minimized.

Analytical modeling of the CVI process has been reported in Refs.[4-6,8-10]. Ref.[4,5] predicts the effect of modifications to the process and of change in preform structure; an one dimensional approach has been applied. Ref.[6] examines the diffusion process in a two-dimensional preform, and a modified van den Brekel model is used to calculate the deposition profile of the porous media. In Ref.[7], both experimental and analytical results for TiC deposition on the inner surface of a capillary for infinitely long time are reported. In Refs.[8-10], a capillary model is used to simulate the CVI process for a unidirectional fiber reinforced ceramic composite. The growth history of alumina and titanium carbide matrix within the capillary is analyzed. The proper reactor condition is recommend based upon the theoretical analysis.

This paper examines the CVI process for a unidirectional preform in an isothermal reactor and a 3-dimensional woven preform in a reactor with pressure and temperature gradients. The objectives of this paper are to predict (1) the densification profile during the process, (2) proper reactor condition and the porosity - time - reactor condition relations for an isothermal CVI process, and (3) the processing time as influenced by the reactor conditions. An approximate solution for the isothermal fabrication process has been obtained. Based on this solution as well as considerations of the chemical reaction rate and diffusivities in different reactor conditions in an isothermal process, the deposition rate and thickness can be predicted. The deposition of both alumina and titanium carbide within the inner wall of a capillary has been considered. A good agreement has been achieved in the comparison of theoretical predictions and experimental data of Ref.[8] for the deposition profiles of TiC. A computational technique has been

developed to study the temperature and pressure gradient processing problem; the vapor velocity and temperature distribution within the preform are examined in this paper.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

(1) Isothermal Process

Basic Assumptions

The modeling analysis considers a unidirectional compact fiber bundle situated in a reactor. The following assumptions are made regarding the fiber preform and vapor deposition process:

1. The fibers of identical radius in the bundle are arranged in a hexagonal-close-packed array.
2. The cross-section of the void space between the fibers is circular in shape.
3. Vapors in the reactor are homogeneous.
4. The first order chemical reactions of the vapor species within the preform are heterogeneous.
5. No bulk flow in capillary during the CVI process.

The chemical vapor reactions for the deposition of Al_2O_3 and TiC within a preform are

and

respectively.

Governing Equation and Boundary Conditions

The conservation of mass in a control volume in cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, z) is considered. Based upon the above assumptions, the governing equation for the i -th species of a multicomponent system becomes

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} - \frac{CD}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial x_i}{\partial r} \right) - CD \frac{\partial^2 x_i}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Here, C is the mole of the total vapor per unit volume (mole / m^3) and t denotes time (sec). D is diffusivity (m^2/sec). x_i is the molar fraction of the i -th species. In the case of steady state and defining $x_i = C_i/C$, the governing equation is reduced to

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial x_i}{\partial r} \right) + r \frac{\partial^2 x_i}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Let $X_i = x_i - x_{i0}$, Eq.(5) is rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial X_i}{\partial r} \right) + r \frac{\partial^2 X_i}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

The boundary conditions of the problem are:

$$1. X_i = 0 \text{ at } z = 0 \text{ and } L \quad (7)$$

$$2. X_i \text{ is finite at } r = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$3. X_i(R, z) = \frac{N_{iR}(z)}{Ck} - x_{i0} \quad (9)$$

The solution of the governing equation is

$$X_i(r,z) = \sum E_m I_0\left(\frac{m\pi r}{L}\right) \sin\left(\frac{m\pi z}{L}\right) \quad (10)$$

where

$$E_m = \frac{-4 \frac{x_{i0}}{(2m+1)\pi}}{I_0\left(\frac{(2m+1)\pi R}{L}\right) + \frac{D}{k} \frac{(2m+1)\pi}{L} I_1\left(\frac{(2m+1)\pi R}{L}\right)}$$

I_0 and I_1 denote the Bessel functions.

Diffusion Coefficients

The diffusion coefficient, D , in the vapor deposition process varies with temperature, pressure, vapor composition, and the pore diameter. The dominating diffusion processes can be categorized by the ratio of the mean free path of molecules, $\lambda(m)$, to the average pore radius, $r(m)$, as following

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\lambda}{2r} &\geq 10 : \text{Knudsen diffusion} \\ 0.01 &\leq \frac{\lambda}{2r} \leq 10 : \text{transition region diffusion} \\ 0.01 &\leq \frac{\lambda}{2r} : \text{molecular diffusion} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Reaction Rate Constant

The reaction rate constant adopted in the present calculation is based upon the Arrhenius equation:

$$k = A_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (12)$$

where A_0 : constant ($\text{m}^3/\text{mole}\cdot\text{sec}$), R : gas constant (8.3143 J/K mole), T : temperature (K), and E_a : activation energy (J/mole).

(2) Pressure and Temperature Gradient Process

Basic Assumptions

A three-dimensionally woven fabric can be regarded as a porous media. The following assumptions are made concerning the reactant properties, preform structure, and flow phenomena:

1. The aspect ratio of the rectangular bar shape preform is very large.
2. Fluid flow within the preform satisfies Darcy's law.
3. Reactant properties and compositions remain constant during process.
4. Gravity effect is neglected in the flow process.
5. Thermal equilibrium among matrix, fiber, and reactants in the unit cell is maintained.
6. Deposition is uniform throughout the unit cell.
7. Heat generation by chemical reaction can be neglected due to very slow reaction and force convection flow.

A two dimensional isotropic, homogeneous porous media is assumed. The schematic figure of reactor and fibrous preform are shown in Fig.1. Two impermeable heating element ($T = 1473 \text{ K}$) are located in the upper and left surface of this preform. Furthermore, an isothermal holder ($T = 1073 \text{ K}$) is situated in the lower right corner of the preform. Mixture of vapor reactants comes from the lower surface of the preform

and goes out from the right hand side surface by applying a pressure difference between the inlet and the outlet. The deposition gradient occurs due to the temperature gradient within the preform. Therefore, the growth of the vapor-solid interface from the upper left hand portion of the preform to the lower right hand portion can prevent the premature closure of the preform.

Fig. 1 Schematic figure of fibrous preform in a reactor showing the pressure and temperature gradients.

The assumptions (2 ~ 7) lead to the following governing equations.

$$\nabla \cdot A_v \underline{V} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\underline{V} = -\frac{\kappa}{\mu} \nabla P \quad (14)$$

$$A_v (\underline{V} \cdot \nabla T) = \alpha \nu \cdot A_s \nabla T \quad \alpha = \frac{K}{\rho C_p} \quad (15)$$

where κ , P , T , \underline{V} , K , C_p , ρ denote permeability, pressure, temperature, velocity, conductivity of matrix, specific heat of reactants, and density, respectively. A_s and A_v represent, respectively, the solidified and unsolidified area of the surface of the control volume.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

(1) For Isothermal Process

The deposition thicknesses profile of the final product at two temperatures are examined. A relatively thicker layer is obtained at lower deposition temperature, as expected. Furthermore, the growth rate is obviously higher near the ends of the fiber bundle than at the middle section due to the variation in vapor concentration. Also, at a given section of the fiber bundle, the growth rate decreases with time; this is due to the decrease in inlet area and consequently less vapor can reach this section.

The relationship between Sherwood number ($Sh = KR/D$), which reflects the reactor condition, processing period, and porosity is shown in Fig.2. From this figure, the proper reactor conditions for specific product requirements can be determined. The results of the present analysis which considers a steady state deposition and moving boundary condition agrees with the experimental data of van den Brekel et al ⁷.

Fig. 2 Porosity and processing time at different Sherwood number

(2) Process with Pressure and Temperature Gradients

Fig.3 shows the temperature profile within the preform during the initial stage of the process. As expected, the temperature decreases gradually from the upper left portion of the preform to the lower right portion. The propagation of the densified front can then be predicted from the temperature profiles.

Fig. 3 Temperature distribution within the fibrous preform in initial fabrication stage

CONCLUSIONS

The first part of this paper reviews an analytical model for the isothermal chemical vapor infiltration process. Both diffusivity of vapors and reaction constant are considered. Since the reaction rate constant is more sensitive than the diffusivity, temperature plays a very important role during the manufacturing process.

The second part of this paper examines the flow and thermal fields in a fibrous preform under pressure and temperature gradients, at the initial fabrication stage. The amount of vapor species that can reach the higher temperature region decreases during the deposition process due to the decrease in the permeability of the preform. When the permeability is small enough, free convection may replace forced convection, and the mass transport by diffusion may occur in the later stage of the deposition process.

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